

**A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF GREEN MARKETING ON
CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR
WITH REFERENCE TO AYURVEDIC PRODUCTS.**

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Abstract:

The rapidly growing size of the Indian Ayush market, the increasing awareness about environment conservation and consumer consciousness towards healthy products led to this research evaluating the impact of green marketing on consumer behaviour with reference to Ayurvedic Products. The hypotheses were tested using one sample t test, which revealed that green marketing influences consumer preference and purchase intention of Ayurvedic products. Further, the research also reveals the impact of the pandemic on consumer behaviour.

Introduction:

A report by Research and Information System for Developing Countries (2021) stated the market size of AYUSH has grown by 17 percent in 2014-20 to reach US dollars 18.1 billion. Further, despite the economic slowdown due to the pandemic, it is projected to reach USD 23.3 billion in 2022. The Indian government also wants to promote the Industry by launching the AYUSH mark and AYUSH visas to foreigners to come to India for traditional treatments. The pandemic, gave an added impetus to Ayurvedic products with the government promoting various herbal teas and immunity boosting concoctions based on Ayurveda. With increasing awareness on healthy lifestyles, environmental concerns around climate change, pollution, etc. sustainability and green marketing has become an important area of interest for multi-national corporations, government, academicians and stakeholders over the past decades. This research therefore investigates the impact of green marketing on consumer behaviour with reference to

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Ayurvedic Products.

Theoretical Concepts:

Green Marketing - The American Marketing Association (AMA) defines Green Marketing as Marketing of the products that are presumed to be environmentally safe. Pride and Ferrel (1993): Green Marketing also known as environmental Marketing and Sustainable Marketing refers to an organizations effort of designing, promoting, pricing and distributing products that will not harm the environment. Polonsky (1994): Defines green Marketing as All activities designed to generate and facilitate any in exchanges intended to satisfy human needs or wants, such that satisfaction of these needs and wants occurs with minimal detrimental effect on the natural environment. Peattie (1995): Defined green Marketing as The holistic management process responsible for identifying, anticipating and satisfying the need of customers and society in a profitable and sustainable way. Green marketing refers to the process of selling products and/or services based on their environmental benefits. Such a product or service may be environmentally friendly in itself or produced in an environmentally friendly way, such as: 1. Products with no toxic contents 2. Products which can be recycled 3. Products made from natural ingredients 4. Products with no excess packaging 5. Products which are repairable and reusable and easily disposable.

Consumer Behaviour - According to Kotler (1994) Consumer behaviour is the study of how people buy, what they buy, when they buy and why they buy. According to Solomon et al. (1995) Consumer behaviour is the study “of the processes involved when individuals or groups select, purchase, use, or dispose of products, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy needs and desires.” According to Schiffman (2007) Consumer Behaviour is “the behaviour that consumers display in searching for, purchasing, using, evaluating, and disposing of products and services that they expect will satisfy their needs.” Kotler and Keller (2011) state that consumer buying behaviour is the study of the ways of buying and disposing of goods, services, ideas or experiences by the individuals, groups and organizations in order to satisfy their needs and wants.

Ayurvedic Products - Ayurveda is formed from two words, Ayuh (life) and Veda (knowledge / science). Ayurveda, a science of life, is the most traditional approach of healing

bridging a healthy balance between body, mind, or soul. Ayurvedic products are marketed in forms like tablets, pills, powders, creams, drops, lotions, ointments, herbal oils, teas, plant extracts, etc; for health, wellness, beauty and personal care. This serves as the scope of the term ‘Ayurvedic products’ for this study - products safe for health and made with best aspects of Ayurvedic practices.

Review of Literature:

According to a study by IIED and ETS (2002), Ayurveda, an ancient health system originated around 5,000 years ago with more than 8,000 plants that are already found to have medicinal value. Ayurveda is a system based on notion of balance, predominantly practiced in India and has been in existence for almost five thousand years. (Morgan, 2002)

Consumers in rural areas show more trust in nature based (Ayurvedic) products since they relate these products to indigenous treatment. (Sawant, 2013) The younger female population is more attracted towards natural products. (Anute et. al, 2015)

The Associated Chambers of Commerce and Industry of India (2012) revealed that 72% of corporate employees are turning to traditional treatments like naturopathy, massage, acupuncture and acupressure. Further, brand, advertising, awareness, packaging and availability are important factors that influence perception of the masses towards specific Ayurved branded products. (Kewlani and Singh, 2012). People understand consequences of using harmful chemical based products and also cost of modern medicines which now contributes to a preference for Ayurvedic products. (Sharma et.al., 2008). Misra et. al. (2020) cited Chandiralekha and Hamsalakshmi (2016) on the vital factors for increasing brand preference of Ayurvedic products are use of natural ingredients and their health benefits.

Customers have a significant and positive perception towards herbal cosmetics and are willing to purchase such products at a premium. (Makkar et. al., 2007) There is a growing inclination towards purchasing herbal products, which are supposed to be less damaging, compared to the chemical based products and a majority of customers have brand loyalty towards Ayurvedic products (Vaish, 2006). Rekha and Gokila (2015) revealed that many consumers are moving to herbal based cosmetics as they experienced chemicals in the

cosmetics, which could lead to side effects. Factors like quality, freshness, flavour, colour, brand image and packing have more impact on the customer buying behaviour where a majority were users of Patanjali products. (Singh et. al., 2021)

Research Objectives:

The objectives of this study are:

1. To evaluate the influence of green marketing on consumer preference with reference to Ayurvedic products.
2. To investigate whether green marketing has an effect on purchase intention of Ayurvedic products.
3. To study the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on consumer behaviour with respect to Ayurvedic Products

Research Methodology:

The population under study are consumers located in Maharashtra. Most of which happened to be located in Mumbai and Pune. The sample was selected using the Cluster Sampling Method. The data was collected using an online form. 115 responses were collected. After scanning for errors, responses were eliminated leaving us with 105 responses. The data was analysed using contingency tables, pie charts and the hypotheses were tested using one sample t test.

Hypotheses:

Accordingly, the null and alternate hypotheses are developed as below:

Null Hypotheses	Alternate Hypotheses
H _{0a} – Green Marketing does not influence consumers’ preference towards Ayurvedic products.	H _a – Green Marketing influences consumers’ preference towards Ayurvedic products.
H _{0b} – Green Marketing of Ayurvedic Products has no relation with Purchase Intention of these products.	H _b - Green Marketing of Ayurvedic Products has a relation with Purchase Intention of these products.

H _{0c} – The Covid-19 pandemic has no impact on consumer behaviour with reference to Ayurvedic products.	H _c – The Covid-19 pandemic has an impact on consumer behaviour with reference to Ayurvedic products.
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Data Analysis and Findings:

Socio-Demographic Profile of Survey Respondents:

Age Group	Gender:		
	Female	Male	Total
Below 20 years	17	3	20
20 - 30 years	36	32	68
31 - 40 years	3	6	9
41 - 50 years	5	1	6
51 - 60 years	2	0	2
Total	63	42	105

Age Group	Education Level:				
	Graduate	Post Graduate	Up to Class 10	Up to Class 12	Total
Below 20 years	4	0	1	15	20
20 - 30 years	34	30	0	4	68
31 - 40 years	4	5	0	0	9
41 - 50 years	3	3	0	0	6
51 - 60 years	2	0	0	0	2
Total	47	38	1	19	105

47% respondents said they use Ayurvedic products for body and beauty such as face-wash, soaps, oils, shampoos, make up, hair colour, etc. The second highest preference (36%) was for Ayurvedic medicines, kadhas, etc. for treatment of sicknesses. The top 3 Ayurvedic brands named were Patanjali, Dabur and Himalaya.

One Sample T-Test	t	df	p
I always look for Ayurvedic and natural alternatives to the products I purchase because they are good for health.	2.994	104	0.003

On conducting the one sample t-test to understand consumer’s preference of Ayurvedic and natural products, the p value is 0.003 which is statistically significant. This allows us to accept the alternate hypothesis H_a – Green Marketing influences consumers’ preference of Ayurvedic products.

One Sample T-Test			
	t	df	p
Rate the ‘Use of Chemicals vs Natural Ingredients’ as a factor while purchasing a product.	7.801	104	< .001

A one sample t test showed p value <0.001 which is statistically significant and disproves the null hypothesis Green Marketing of Ayurvedic Products has no relation with Purchase Intention of these products.

The impact of education level on purchase intention considering factors like use of chemicals vs natural ingredients as well as the quality of the product was also analysed. It was found that the p value was 0.003 and <0.001 in the case of use of chemicals vs natural ingredients and quality respectively, which was found to be significant implying that education level of the consumer plays a role in understanding green marketing and the benefits of green products.

One Sample T-Test			
	t	df	p
I started using Ayurvedic products such as herbal cough syrups, teas, kadhas, Chywanprash, etc. during the Covid-19 pandemic	-3.609	104	< .001

To evaluate the Covid-19 impact on consumer behaviour, consumers were asked if they purchased Ayurvedic products such as herbal cough syrups, teas, kadhas, Chywanprash, etc during the pandemic. The p value in the one sample t test was <0.001 and statistically significant allowing us to accept alternate hypothesis H_c – The Covid-19 pandemic has an impact on consumer behaviour with reference to Ayurvedic products.

Conclusion:

The study revealed that green marketing has a significant impact on consumers' preference, behaviour and purchase intention of Ayurvedic products. Further, there is also a relation between Education level and consumer behaviour with respect to these products. With growing awareness of products that must be good and safe for health along with the environment, the demand for Ayurvedic products is estimated to continue on its upward trend.

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